

EOSC-IF

Guidance note: Onboarding an Interoperability Guideline to EOSC

Version 1.0

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EOSC-IF / Guidance note: Onboarding an Interoperability Guideline to EOSC

Lead by **GÉANT**

Authored by Michelle Williams (GÉANT)

Dissemination Level of the Document

Public

Abstract

This document complements the published EOSC Onboarding Team's Onboarding Procedure for Interoperability Guidelines¹, providing additional guidance for users in onboarding an Interoperability Guideline to the EOSC Portal for inclusion in the EOSC Interoperability Framework.

Version History

Version	Date	Authors/Contributors	Description
V0.1	April 2023	Authored by Michelle Williams (GÉANT)	First draft
V1.0	May 2023	Michelle Williams (GÉANT)	Final Version published to Zenodo

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¹

<https://wiki.eoscfuture.eu/display/EOSCOB/EPOT+Procedure-14%3A+Onboard+an+Interoperability+Guideline>

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Glossary

EOSC Future project Glossary is incorporated by reference: <https://wiki.eoscfuture.eu/x/JQCK>

List of Abbreviations

Acronym	Definition
API	Application Programming Interface
DOI	Digital Object Identifier
EOSC-IF	EOSC Interoperability Framework
EPOT	EOSC Portal Onboarding Team
URI	Uniform Resource Identifier
URL	Uniform Resource Locator

1 Introduction

The EOSC-IF will be built upon a wide range of components, such as standards, APIs, policy frameworks, etc. Starting with human-readable interoperability guidelines that aim to promote and facilitate interoperability across services, resources, infrastructures and domains, the Framework will begin to incorporate more executable, machine-readable artefacts that would support composable or executable workflows at a later stage. Guidance notes for writing an EOSC Interoperability Guideline for inclusion in the EOSC Interoperability Framework are provided².

It is assumed that Interoperability Guidelines will be already established and published by an Infrastructure or Scientific Domain/Community, and therefore an author will not intend to write a new Interoperability Guideline for submission to the EOSC Interoperability Framework. However, it is conceivable that an existing Interoperability Guideline or collection of Guidelines would benefit from being structured into an EOSC Interoperability Guideline. In this case, a Word template has been provided³ that is tailored towards Interoperability Guidelines produced under the EOSC Future project, but that can also be utilised (ensuring that the relevant copyright and project funding statements are updated as required), and the following guidance notes can be utilised in producing that document.

Interoperability Guidelines that meet the Inclusion Criteria⁴ can be onboarded to the EOSC Portal using the EOSC Providers Portal.

The EOSC Interoperability Registry allows Providers to onboard a description of the Interoperability Guideline that contains references to the relevant documentation, APIs, protocols, etc that the Guideline recommends. The description 'record' that results from the onboarding procedure is called an 'Interoperability Guideline Profile'.

2 Types of Interoperability Guideline

An **EOSC-Core Interoperability Guideline** describes specifications for the purposes of interoperating resources with EOSC-Core services. EOSC-Core guidelines provide context and description in order to provide technical instructions to scientific resource providers that would like to integrate their services and/or resources with (or be interoperable with) one or more EOSC-Core Services. These guidelines are created by operators of EOSC-Core Services to provide guidance to scientific service and resource providers who wish to benefit from the functionalities that the EOSC-Core services offer.

An **EOSC-Exchange Interoperability Guideline** (thematic/community) refers to where thematic or community services and resources interoperate with each other, usually at a domain level such as Cluster-specific. These guidelines are created by scientific community experts to provide guidance to their communities and highlight the importance of their interoperability efforts at the European-wide EOSC level. They are further intended to increase awareness of the existing thematic and community accomplishments to facilitate/increase interoperability relating to specific domains.

An **EOSC-Exchange Interoperability Guideline (horizontal)** refers to where services and resources interoperate with each other across communities and infrastructures. These are important at the EOSC Exchange level to help EOSC facilitate cross-linking of services and resources while staying domain-agnostic. These are of wider applicability than the thematic/horizontal guidelines and have a much broader scope. These guidelines are created by scientific community experts to provide guidance to their own community and highlight their importance at the European-wide EOSC level. However, this, similarly, makes them more difficult to develop and requires cross-Cluster engagement and representation to ensure they are well-rounded and widely applicable to a diverse range of intended guideline users.

² Guidance note: Writing a Guideline for the EOSC Interoperability Framework: 10.5281/zenodo.7929870

³ <https://eosc-portal.eu/eosc-interoperability-framework/eosc-if-templates-and-information>

⁴

<https://wiki.eoscfuture.eu/display/EOSCSMS/EOSC-Exchange+inclusion+criteria#EOSCExchangeinclusioncriteria-3.6.Additionalinclusioncriteriatoonboardaninteroperabilityguideline>

3 How to Onboard an Interoperability Guideline for inclusion in the EOSC Interoperability Framework

Please note, it is assumed that the owner of the Interoperability Guideline already has a Provider Profile within the EOSC Providers Portal and has administration rights for the related Provider Profile. If not, please refer to further instructions in the EOSC Provider Hub for creating such a Profile.

The Provider will be treated as the lead organisation for the Interoperability Guideline to be onboarded, but additional creators can be added to the Interoperability Guideline Profile.

Instruction	Detail
Log into the EOSC Providers Portal	providers.eosc-portal.eu/home
<p>Select My Providers and then select the relevant Provider to be updated.</p> <p>(Note: it is necessary to be an authorised admin of the Provider)</p>	
The 'Add new Guideline' option can be selected from inside the Provider dashboard.	

3.1 Describe the Interoperability Guideline

<p>The Provider Representative is asked to complete a two-page form that is based on the EOSC Interoperability Guideline Profile⁵.</p> <p>The attributes are based on the Data Cite Metadata Scheme 4.4⁶, and the guidance below should help to clarify how these attributes should be completed in the context of Interoperability Guidelines for the EOSC.</p>	
<p>Identifier</p>	<p>The Identifier is a unique string that identifies the Guideline. This is likely to be the DOI or URI where the document is published. DOI is preferred. Note that this must be unique, and the URL inserted here will be treated as the primary key.</p>
<p>Identifier Type</p>	<p>Select the Identifier Type from the drop down list.</p>
<p>Title</p>	<p>The name or title by which the Guideline is known. The title will influence the search results returned by the users that look for Interoperability Guidelines, so it should be as concise and specific as feasible. Maximum 250 characters allowed.</p>
<p>Publication Year</p>	<p>The year when the guideline was or will be made publicly available. If an embargo period has been in effect, use the date when the embargo period ends.</p>
<p>Resource Type</p>	<p>This should be a brief abstract description of the resource, and should include the nature of the Guideline, i.e., whether it is API, metadata schema, specification, policy, framework, human-readable guideline, human readable guideline, configuration template. Maximum 1000 characters allowed.</p>
<p>Resource Type General</p>	<p>This will default to 'Guideline' in order to signal an Interoperability Guideline in the EOSC Marketplace; additional values will be added to the Controlled</p>

⁵ <https://wiki.eoscfuture.eu/display/PUBLIC/EOSC+Interoperability+Guideline+Profile+--+Data+Model>

⁶ DataCite Metadata Working Group. (2021). DataCite Metadata Schema Documentation for the Publication and Citation of Research Data and Other Research Outputs. Version 4.4. DataCite e.V. <https://doi.org/10.14454/3W3Z-SA82>

	Vocabulary for this field in future releases.
Related Standards	<p>This attribute is designed to capture details regarding the main standards, protocols, APIs, etc., that are adopted by this Interoperability Guideline. This should point to related standards only when it is a prerequisite/dependency, and where it is likely to influence the manner in which a Provider would design towards interoperability based on the guideline. Multiple Related Standards can be added. Maximum 250 characters allowed.</p> <p>The Related Standard URI field should be filled with the related URI. A human-readable name is to be added in the 'Related Standard Identifier' field.</p>
Rights	<p>The 'Rights' field is mandatory, and should include any rights information related to the Guideline. The property may be repeated to record complex rights characteristics. The Provider must include a rights management statement for the resource or reference a service providing such information. Include embargo information if applicable. Use the complete title of a license and include version information if applicable. May be used for software licenses. Examples: Creative Commons Attribution, 3.0 Germany License, Apache License, Version 2.026. Maximum 500 characters allowed.</p>
Rights URI	This field should be completed with the URI relating to the rights statement.
Rights Identifier	This field should be completed with the short, standardised version of the license name. Example: CC-BY-3.0.
Description	<p>Complete the box on the left-hand side with a summary of the guideline. The description can include additional information that does not fit in any of the other categories and may be used for technical information.</p> <p>Consider including a concise description of the main features and benefits of interoperation in the manner described, and a brief description of the use case, problem statement, gap or need that this interoperability addresses.</p> <p>The box on the left-hand side allows formatting, and the box on the right allows you to see how the text will be represented in the UI. Maximum 500 characters allowed.</p>
Status	<p>Providers should initially select the 'Proposed' value from the drop-down menu. The EPOT team will select and/or advise the most</p>

	appropriate value during the Onboarding procedure. This field relates to the status of the Guideline in relation to its inclusion in the EOSC Interoperability Framework, and not to the lifecycle status of the related APIs, standards, protocols, service, product, etc.
Domain	Please select the most appropriate top-level Domain to which the Guideline applies from the drop-down menu. Guidelines that can be utilised across all domains can be classified as 'Generic'.
EOSC Guideline Type	Please select the most appropriate Guideline Type from the drop-down menu. Please refer to section 2 above for more guidance.
EOSC Integration Options	This optional attribute is generally applicable to EOSC-Core Interoperability Guidelines, where a number of types of Integration can be achieved with a Core Service. This field may not be applicable to all types of Interoperability Guideline.

3.2 Describe the Creators of the Interoperability Guideline

<p>The second page of the form relates to the Creators of the Guideline. The Creator field is optional, but it can be used when multiple authors, organisations, communities, projects or initiatives have been involved in the creation of the Guideline.</p> <p>Creators can be organisations as well as people, but please note that the Provider that onboards the Interoperability Guideline will be its lead organisation, rather than any Creator organisation captured in this form.</p> <p>Please create a Creator form for each Creator to be cited.</p>	<p>The screenshot shows a form titled 'Creators' with the following fields and descriptions:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Creator Name: The full name of the creator. Can be organisation or personal name. Examples: Charpy, Antoine; Jemison, Mae; Foo Data Center. Names in non-roman scripts may be transliterated according to the ALA-LC tables. Name Type (*): The type of name. Options: Personal. Given Name: The personal or first name of the creator. Family Name: The surname or last name of the creator. Name Identifier: Uniquely identifies an individual or legal entity, according to various schemes. Affiliation: The organizational or institutional affiliation of the creator. The creator's nameType may be Organizational or Personal. In the case of an organizational creator, e.g., a research group, this will often be the name of the institution to which that organization belongs. Affiliation Identifier: Uniquely identifies the organizational affiliation of the creator. The format is dependent upon scheme. Examples: https://ror.org/04q4c1811 grant:40181/3 <p>At the bottom of the form is a '+ Add creator' button.</p>
Creator Name	This is the full name of the creator. Can be an organisation or a personal name. Examples: Charpy, Antoine; Jemison, Mae; Foo Data Center. Names in non-roman scripts may be transliterated according to the ALA-LC tables.

Name Type	This field allows the user onboarding the Interoperability Guideline to specify whether the Creator Name is personal or the name of an organisation.
Given Name	The personal or first name of the creator.
Family Name	The surname or last name of the creator.
Name Identifier	This optional field uniquely identifies an individual or legal entity, and can be used to add a Name Identifier according to the required scheme.
Affiliation	This optional field can be used to convey the organisational or institutional affiliation of the creator. The creator's nameType may be Organisational or Personal. In the case of an organisational creator, e.g., a research group, this will often be the name of the institution to which that organisation belongs.
Affiliation Identifier	This optional field can be used to uniquely identify the organisational affiliation of the creator. The format depends on the scheme. Examples: https://ror.org/04aj4c181 grid.461819.3
When the forms are complete, scroll to the top of the page and click 'Submit. At this point a new ID will be assigned in the Registry's database and the form will commence the EOSC Onboarding Procedure for Interoperability Guidelines, where a member of the EOSC-IF Governance team will help you through the process.	<p>The screenshot shows a blue button labeled "Add New Guideline" with a "Submit" button next to it. Below the main button, it says "id will be assigned automatically".</p>

4 Viewing and Maintaining Interoperability Guidelines

It is possible to view a summary of a Pending, Approved or Rejected Interoperability Guideline Profile in the Provider Dashboard, and to edit or delete the Profile itself.

MONITOR

- Statistics**
- Update History
- Info
- Services
- Shared Services
- Draft Services
- Training Resources
- Guidelines** ←
- Messages

ACTIONS

- Add new Service
- Add new Datasource
- Add new Training Resource
- Add new Guideline
- Update Provider
- Delete Provider
- Use API

Info
Services
Shared Services
Draft Services
Training Resources
Guidelines
Messages

ACTIONS

- Add new Service
- Add new Datasource
- Add new Training Resource
- Add new Guideline
- Update Provider
- Delete Provider

Results per page 10 Order Ascending Order by Title Status All Search...

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Pending

EOSC Security Operational Baseline 2022

To fulfil its mission, it is necessary for the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC) to be protected from damage, disruption, and unauthorised use. This Security Baseline supports these goals by defining minimum expectations and requirements of the behaviour of those offering services to users and communities connected to the EOSC, and of those providing access to services or assembling service components through the EOSC. It aims to establish a sufficient level of trust between all Participants in the Infrastructure to enable reliable and secure Infrastructure operation.

Creation Date: May 12, 2023
Last Update: May 12, 2023

Update Guidelines
Delete Guidelines

Provide feedback

5 Related documents

- EPOT Procedure-14: Onboard an Interoperability Guideline (relating to EPOT team activities).⁷
- Guidance note: Writing a Guideline for the EOSC Interoperability Framework: 10.5281/zenodo.7929870
- Guidance note: Reviewing a Guideline for the EOSC Interoperability Framework: 10.5281/zenodo.7929900
- Guidance note: Assigning an Interoperability Guideline to an EOSC Service Profile: 10.5281/zenodo.7929856
- EOSC Interoperability Guideline Profile Data Model

References

- [1] Eosc-portal.eu. 2021. EOSC Portal. [online] Available at: <<https://eosc-portal.eu/>>
- [2] EOSC Onboarding Inclusion Criteria, [online] Available at: <https://wiki.eoscfuture.eu/display/EOSCSMS/EOSC-Exchange+inclusion+criteria>
- [3] Data Cite Metadata Schema 4.4, 201 [online] Available at: DataCite Metadata Working Group. (2021). DataCite Metadata Schema Documentation for the Publication and Citation of Research Data and Other Research Outputs. Version 4.4. DataCite e.V. <https://doi.org/10.14454/3w3z-sa82>
- [4] EOSC Interoperability Guideline Profile Data Model [online] Available at: <https://wiki.eoscfuture.eu/display/PUBLIC/EOSC+Interoperability+Guideline+Profile+-+Data+Model>

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<https://wiki.eoscfuture.eu/display/EOSCOB/EPOT+Procedure-14%3A+Onboard+an+Interoperability+Guideline>